

Adaptation of Educational Materials for Students with Visual Disability: Innovative Approaches and Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract

Ensuring accessibility in education for students with visual disability, which encompasses a spectrum of conditions ranging from low vision to complete blindness, is critical for their equitable participation in academic activities. This literature review examines the adaptation of educational materials through both traditional and innovative approaches, including the application of Artificial Intelligence. The analysis encompasses visual, typographic, auditory, tactile, and technological adaptations that contribute to enhanced access and improved learning experiences. Additionally, the study presents Artificial Intelligence applications, such as personal assistants and adaptive learning systems, which enhance the autonomy and social integration of students with visual disability. The findings underscore the necessity for the continuous enhancement of adaptations and educational policies to foster an inclusive educational environment, as well as the imperative for ongoing professional development for educators.

Key Words: educational adaptations, visual disability, Artificial Intelligence

Introduction

Accessibility in education is fundamental to ensuring that equal educational opportunities are provided to all students, regardless of disability or learning difficulties. Students with visual disability (VD) may have significantly reduced visual acuity, even after the best corrective measures are applied (low vision), or they may experience severe VD, including congenital or complete blindness (Glatz et al., 2022). Some students with low vision may be able to read large print or use magnification devices, while others might rely more heavily on non-visual senses and assistive technologies (Presley & D'Andrea, 2008). In this context, students with VD face substantial challenges as they strive to adapt and succeed in an educational environment that is often not tailored to meet their needs (Ulldemolins et al., 2012). These challenges are manifold and can be practical, social, psychological, and economic, making the educational process difficult for them (Amin et al., 2021). The importance of accessibility in the education of students with VD is demonstrated through the creation of an adapted learning environment where they can develop their skills, overcome barriers, participate actively, and achieve their educational goals in an equitable and fair manner. Furthermore, they are empowered in their personal and social lives (Mason & McCall, 2013).

Educational differentiation for students with VD requires the implementation of specific strategies, methods, practices, and adaptive tools to provide a fully inclusive learning experience. This allows students with VD to develop academically and socially, contributing to the achievement of their personal and professional goals (Morris, 2014). In practice, the limited availability of adapted educational materials constitutes a significant issue, as these resources are crucial for effective and autonomous learning (Adebimpe et al., 2014). Providing such materials can greatly enhance the ability of students with VD to access educational content and participate in courses, thereby profoundly influencing their overall learning experience (Olaopa, 2017). Consequently, research into appropriate approaches for creating adapted educational materials for students with VD continues to be of significant scientific interest worldwide (Miyauchi, 2020).

This literature review seeks to explore the effectiveness of both traditional and innovative approaches, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), in adapting educational materials for students with VD. By integrating technological and non-technological methods, the goal is to provide a comprehensive overview that can guide educators, policymakers, and researchers in developing more inclusive educational environments.

Visual and Typographic Adaptations

The implementation of visual and typographic adaptations in educational materials is a fundamental factor in ensuring equal access to education for students with VD (Kizilaslan, 2020). The use of larger font sizes has been historically chosen as a typographic adaptation that allows students with low vision to read educational texts more easily, improving clarity (Arditi, 2004). Additionally, the adaptation of educational materials typically favors clear fonts without unnecessary artistic elements to enhance readability, while also considering factors such as avoiding glossy paper and maintaining a clear, uncluttered page layout to facilitate comprehension (Dunn & Darlington, 2016). Some students with VD may also require further adjustments in the spacing between characters and the height or orientation of the text (McLeish, 2007). For example, the Tiresias and Matilda fonts were specifically engineered for visually impaired readers, incorporating a larger x-height, open letterforms, and generous spacing, and have demonstrably improved reading speed and accuracy compared to widely used fonts such as Times New Roman or Helvetica (Rubin et al., 2006; Bessemans, 2016). Similarly, the adoption of sans-serif fonts like Verdana in large print textbooks, particularly at 18-point size or larger, significantly enhanced readability for students with VD (Connolly et al., 2010; Uysal & Duger, 2012).

In addition, the practice of improving the contrast of textual and graphic elements in educational materials enhances accessibility and readability for students with VD (Singleton & Neuber, 2020). This type of adaptation increases the visual distinctiveness of the material, aiding students in addressing their learning needs more effectively (Wambua & Oboko, 2015). High color contrast is one of the most significant approaches, as specific color combinations facilitate readability and reduce visual fatigue (Cox & Dykes, 2001). Likewise, the use of sans-serif fonts contributes to the proper contrast of text characters. The simple and continuous lines of such fonts make letters more distinguishable and readable (Evetts & Brown, 2005). The distinctiveness of text sections can be increased by using bolder fonts for headings and color differentiation for various sections, making it easier for students with VD to quickly locate information in educational texts (Rosenblum et al., 2018).

The application of visual and typographic principles is not limited exclusively to textbooks but extends to other printed educational materials, such as educational presentations, exam papers, worksheets, and digital educational materials, including websites and educational multimedia (Leinenbach & Corey, 2004; Lazar et al., 2015). Additionally, in digital educational materials hosted on e-books, educational websites, applications, and platforms, the availability of pre-configured typographic adaptations (large fonts/high contrast/dark mode) is also critical. This allows students with VD to choose from a variety of ready-made visual

settings that can immediately enhance the visibility and readability of the material, automatically tailoring it to their individual needs and preferences (Firth, 2024).

Auditory and Tactile Adaptations

Educational audiobooks represent a traditional strategy for the auditory adaptation of educational material for students with VD (Wolfson, 2008). Audiobooks in education include recorded readings of entire texts of educational material, either by professional narrators or by the authors themselves, and are available through public libraries, specialized institutions for individuals with VD, or educational online platforms (Guha, 2021). Educational audiobooks are suitably designed for educational use and often come with pedagogical guidelines. They are available in various formats and originate from different cognitive fields, ensuring access to a wide range of educational material (Ry-Kottah et al., 2022). Audiobooks cover a broad spectrum of educational, literary, and scientific texts, enhancing learning autonomy and access to information, while simultaneously improving language skills and active listening ability (Jackson & Presley, 2012; Subagya, 2017). Moreover, they provide significant flexibility, as they can be used independently by students with VD in multiple educational environments (Setiawan et al., 2020).

One of the primary methods for adapting educational material for tactile use is converting it into a Braille reading and writing system to ensure appropriate rendering and readability for students with VD (Erickson & Hatton, 2007). In these cases, the original text is converted into Braille using specialized software that ensures the correct encoding of the text and compatibility with Braille printers or tactile devices (Ludi & Reichlmayr, 2008; Sawant et al., 2021). As an approach, the use of Braille printing systems accommodates a variety of types and sizes of printed educational materials, with the capability of applying two-dimensional or three-dimensional printing methods (2D - 3D Printable Braille) (Amburgy & Estell, 2024). Expanding accessibility through Braille conversion involves comprehensive adaptation of all educational materials, such as books, workbooks, and examination papers, maintaining the accuracy of the translation into Braille for texts, images, geometric shapes, diagrams, and other graphic elements (Mukherjee et al., 2014). Such approaches require detailed planning to ensure that the tactile elements are functional and comprehensible (Jakoube, 2012).

Technological Adaptations

To ensure an inclusive educational experience for students with VD using digital educational materials, adherence to international accessibility standards is crucial. These standards, including the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG), provide essential guidelines for making online content navigable and usable for students with VD (Hauge, 2021; Panda & Kaur, 2023). The WCAG emphasizes the need for content to be perceivable by offering alternatives to visual media, such as audio descriptions and screen readers, and ensuring sufficient contrast in text and images for readability (Bocevaska et al., 2018; Hajduk & Ali, 2023). Additionally, these guidelines advocate for the use of various assistive technologies and alternative navigation methods, allowing students with VD to independently navigate the internet (Ferati et al., 2016). Content organization should be consistent and easily understandable to facilitate effective navigation (Kumar et al., 2021). Furthermore, WCAG stresses that accessibility must be maintained as technology evolves, ensuring that educational websites and applications remain reliably accessible despite technological advancements (Kimogol, 2023).

Within this framework, the use of specialized software that enables equal access to knowledge and autonomous learning is a critical aspect of adapting educational material for students with VD (Hasselbring & Glaser, 2000; Nisbet, 2020). A primary category of such software includes screen readers, which allow students with VD to listen to educational content displayed on a screen by converting written text into speech. This enables students with VD to navigate menus, read digital documents, and browse educational websites

(Borodin et al., 2010; Ashok et al., 2015). Similarly, specialized software can convert entire educational text materials into audio files (text-to-speech applications), detaching the use of educational material from its adapted version and providing various learning opportunities and educational differentiation (Karkar et al., 2018; Shirly et al., 2018).

Supportive technologies are specifically designed to assist the education of individuals with VD (Martiniello et al., 2020). These include programs that facilitate the acquisition of the Braille system, audio educational games, and interactive learning tools with visual and auditory adaptations (Neto et al., 2020; Senjam et al., 2021). These educational tools enhance autonomy, interaction, and learning efficiency, providing multisensory experiences that are both accessible and enjoyable (Kisanga & Kisanga, 2022). Additionally, innovative object recognition applications utilize the camera of smart devices to identify and describe objects or people in real-time. They use GPS location receivers to provide movement instructions through voice guidance or vibration alerts, offering an innovative adaptation of learning activities and enriching the educational experience for students with VD (Sharmila et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2021).

The implementation of WCAG standards, while designed to enhance digital inclusivity, often necessitates substantial financial and technological resources, which may be scarce in resource-constrained environments (Hollier, 2015; Rao et al., 2017). Moreover, the efficacy of WCAG-compliant websites can be compromised by inadequate internet infrastructure, as these sites frequently require significant bandwidth for optimal functionality (Sloan, 2002). Despite these impediments, the advent of cost-effective and open-source solutions, exemplified by the NVDA screen reader and content management systems such as Joomla and Drupal, offers pragmatic approaches to augmenting digital accessibility without incurring prohibitive expenses (O'Connor, 2007; Soic et al., 2017; Jokinen, 2020).

Adaptations through AI

AI is increasingly playing a crucial role in customizing educational materials for students with VD, enhancing both accessibility and interactivity (Kumar et al., 2023). AI systems are capable of recognizing objects, analyzing information from texts or other educational media, converting them into audio messages, and integrating with other existing technologies and systems (Khan et al., 2020). Such AI software has the potential to serve as a personal assistant, facilitating the real-time adaptation of educational materials based on voice commands from students with VD (Lee & Cho, 2022). Additionally, these AI tools could support the organization of educational tasks, facilitate internet navigation, provide access to information, and generally offer a tailored educational experience based on the diverse needs of each student with VD (Mahendran et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2023).

Learning for students with VD can be significantly enhanced using AI, as adaptive learning systems personalize instruction while AI-powered simulations provide safe environments for skill development (Seo et al., 2021; Mina et al., 2023). Furthermore, interactive educational tools with AI enhance engagement (Khribi, 2022) and offer immediate, personalized feedback (Afzaal et al., 2021). In addition, AI improves accessibility by converting multimedia to text or audio formats (Heidt, 2024). Likewise, AI-enabled collaboration tools facilitate real-time interaction with peers and educators, while digital social integration assistants promote group participation (Walter, 2024).

Building on these advancements, AI-powered screen readers like Microsoft's Narrator, Apple's VoiceOver, and Google's TalkBack assist students with VD in navigating digital content (Vtyurina, 2021). Similarly, AI-based Braille translation tools, such as Dot Translate, convert digital text into Braille (Kakade, 2019). Moreover, applications like Microsoft's Seeing AI and the AI-powered navigation app Aira use computer vision and AI to help students with VD navigate their environment and identify objects around them (Arabic et al., 2024). Large Language Models like ChatGPT also facilitate interaction with technology through voice commands and spoken responses (Kuzdeuov et al., 2024). Despite these advances, significant

research gaps persist, particularly in interpreting complex visual content, integrating AI in real-time classroom settings, and developing more advanced tactile and haptic feedback systems (Chaple et al., 2024).

Considering these factors, the support of educators is vital. Specialized training programs are necessary to equip educators with the expertise to proficiently utilize AI in enhancing the instruction of students with VD (Crompton & Burke, 2023). Additionally, ongoing professional development opportunities can help educators stay updated on the latest advancements in AI and accessible educational materials, fostering a more inclusive and supportive learning environment (Mohammed & Nell Watson, 2019). This approach not only enhances the learning experience for students with VD but also empowers educators with the knowledge and skills to implement innovative teaching strategies effectively (Nazaretsky et al., 2022).

Conclusion

This literature review provides a detailed examination of both technological and non-technological approaches for adapting educational materials to meet the needs of students with VD. The research underscores the critical importance of adapting educational materials to support inclusion and differentiated learning. Contemporary trends highlight the use of traditional techniques - such as visual, typographic, auditory, and tactile adaptations - while integrating new technologies to ensure equal access to knowledge, autonomous learning, and interactive educational experiences. This approach ensures that the educational process is accessible and equitable for all. In particular, the emergence of advanced technological systems, especially those incorporating AI, presents groundbreaking opportunities for enhancing educational methodologies for students with VD. These systems seamlessly blend traditional and modern approaches, exemplified by digital personal assistants. Consequently, prioritizing the continuous development and improvement of personalized methods for adapting educational materials should be a key focus within educational policies, fostering an inclusive and differentiated educational environment for students with VD. Specific areas where additional research is needed include the development of AI-driven tools tailored for diverse learning environments, the long-term impact of these technologies on educational outcomes for students with VD, and the effectiveness of hybrid approaches that combine traditional and digital adaptations in fostering inclusive education.

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